

A STUDY OF GREEN-READINESS POLICY AND GOVERNANCE IN SELECTED SOUTHWESTERN NIGERIA UNIVERSITIES.

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ABSTRACT

The study assessed the policies in institutions of higher learning for green computing-readiness, the IT governance of the institutions and identified the factors preventing the institutions from adopting green computing solution. A cross sectional survey design was employed. Multi stage sampling procedure was adopted. Three universities from the south western states of Nigeria were purposively sampled for the study (one federal, one state and one private) the management and administrative staff of the universities were conveniently sampled. An adopted questionnaire was used to elicit information from the participants. The results revealed that Green policy readiness was found to be above average, however specific green information technology policy was not in place in many of the institutions. Green data centers were not in place and practices of e- waste disposals not still eco-friendly. Readiness for green IT operations and practices were reasonably high. Green IT sourcing is gradually is being moderately implemented. The same goes for end of life practice. Green readiness in governance was also found to be at an average level. Factors impeding green IT readiness in the institutions were predominantly lack of government incentives, cost of IT solutions and lack of enforcement among others.

Key words: Policy, Green Computing, Readiness, Institutions, Nigeria

The safe management of computing and ICT use are fast becoming an issue of critical global concern. This is as a result of its contribution to hazardous ecosystem thus endangering the health of humans (Wildermans et al., 2005). With an increase in the use of technology to improve quality of life and productivity is the increase in the use of computers in workplaces. As computers age and are carelessly disposed, upsurge in human exposure to health issues such as, anemia, nervous disorders, kidney and liver damage, auditory impairment, learning disorders, decreased IQ, Gastrointestinal damage, behavioral disorder, Alzheimer's disease and cancers are being recorded. These electronic goods do not disintegrate but are left on the soil with all their dangerous parts which end up being washed by rain

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water into the streams as well as drained into the soils to be taken up by plants which are ultimately consumed. Mercury which is a major element contained in this e-products is a major cause of many terrible illnesses affecting the brain, liver, kidney, reproductive and digestive systems. These illnesses can result when mercury is inhaled, drunk or eaten or come in contact with skin. Other dangerous components of e-waste are lead, zinc, hexavalent chromium, cadmium, selenium, chromium, arsenics (Elytus, 2019). To mitigate these challenges, the idea and concept of green computing evolved as early as 1992. Green Computing is the environmentally responsible and eco-friendly use of computers and their resources (Goyal, 2023). It borders on environmentally-safe design, manufacturing, use and disposal of computing and other IT resources. This includes the development of environmentally sustainable production practices, energy efficient computer, improved disposals of obsolete parts and recycling procedures (Mmeah, Baah & Akpan, 2018). In practical term green computing practices such as power management, virtualization, cloud computing, optimizing data center design, recycling, proper electronic waste disposal, and optimization of the IT infrastructure helps to meet sustainability requirements in IT services. The adoption of G – computing involves the use of computers and related gadgets that consume less power, lower carbon dioxide emissions, conserve resources, and reduce risks to both human and the environment (Sreenandana, et al; 2020). Green computing practices can be applied in IT based industries data centers towards CO₂ emissions reduction, cost incurred reduction, proper and ethical waste management, depletion of natural resources reduction and high energy utilization decrease (Bakolo & Noraini, 2015). Many of the developed nations are developing policies towards the adoption of green computing. The European Union has since adopted an environmental protection policy where their companies adopt the International Standard for the company-wide environmental management systems (Nashitani, 2010; Neumayer et al., 2004). Similar policies had also been adopted in the U.S and the countries belonging to EU. In Nigeria, there are policies and legislations on environmental protection but there are no clear-cut specialized machineries to detect, measure and confront the environmental menace attributed to electronic dumping and operations of data centers. In other words, the existing environmental policies and legislations are not ICT-specific. It was felt that the various environmental protection policies and legislation did not envisage the current level of advancement in computer technology use (Nwakwo, Akinola & Ukhurebo; 2020). Because of this, Nigeria is fast becoming a dumping ground for used computers and other electronic products from other nations such as US, UK, Germany and China etc. The Nigerian streets are all littered with these items which most of the time have either exceeded their end of life (EOL) or almost exceeded it. This electronic goods end up on dunghills with its attendant health challenges. Apart from national policies, institutional

policies are needed and are in place in many civilized climes such as government parastatals, private establishments and institutions of higher learning.

Since the invasion of Covid-19 in the year 2020, there has been and increased ICT deployments in various workplaces leading to different ICT policies in many of the institutions. It is not known how the policies addressed various contemporary eco-friendly concerns regarding ICT use. This study singled out institutions of higher learning as domain of investigation as it was one of the critical sectors affected by COVID-19 and lengthy lockdown in Nigeria and the world over. Because of the pandemic, ICT use in education has increased tremendously than it has ever been. Apart from the foregoing, institutions of higher learning (as custodians of knowledge) should be at the fore front of responsible and safe ICT usage thus serving as pace-setters to the public. Increased ICT use will still be witnessed in educational sectors in the coming years as Open and Distance Learning are now in vogue. it is imperative to look at the readiness of institutions of learning at adapting green computing. G-computing practice will introduce recyclability and biodegradability, promote paperless policies and reduce print volumes encouraging the adoption of conference calls and the use of blank screensavers option and hibernation (Wibowo, Nada, Novita & Budirahardjo , 2019). The institutions of learning are expected to be pioneers of such innovations and also policy advisers to government, it becomes necessary to examine how prepared the institutions are in adopting the practice of green computing. In an earlier work, Jegede & Elesemoyo (2023) examined the green computing attitude and technology deployment of selected higher institutions of learning. The preparation goes beyond (though include) favourable attitudinal disposition or deploying appropriate technology. It is key to examine if appropriate policy is in place and what such policy documents stipulate as well as the implementation of same. This is what the current study seeks to investigate.

.The following objectives will guide the study;

- i) Assess institutional policies in the area of IT sourcing, IT operations and IT end of life management of green computing.
- ii) Assess the IT governance of the institutions.
- iii) Identify the factors or challenges that might prevent institutions from successfully adopting green solution.

METHODS

The study made use of a cross sectional survey design .Three universities (one federal, one state and one private) were purposefully selected from the southwestern geopolitical zone of Nigeria for the study. The administrative and management officers of the universities were conveniently sampled. These included: the heads of

departments, directors of institutes and directorates, deans of faculties etc. Some sections of a questionnaire developed by Molla, Cooper & Pittayachawan (2011). was adopted for data collection. These sections included Institutional policies which had been put in place to ensure green computing, the questions here covered such aspects as green IT sourcing, IT operations and IT end of life (EOL) management, the second aspect elicited responses on the IT governance of the institutions through green IT initiatives and the third sought to identify factors that are preventing institutions from adopting green IT solutions. One hundred and twenty (120) questionnaires were administered but only 77 were returned. The resulting data were analyzed using descriptive statistics.

RESULTS

Table 1: Green-Readiness Policy

S/ N	Our institution has:	Not at all (1)	Small Extent (2)	Moderate Extent (3)	Great Extent (4)	Very Great Extent (5)	μ
1	a policy that states staff should turn off computers when they are not in use	14 (19.18%)	15 (20.55%)	10 (13.70%)	18 (24.66%)	16 (21.92%)	3.10
2	a policy to minimize waste and increase recycling policy	15 (20.83%)	9 (12.50%)	20 (27.78%)	12 (16.67%)	16 (22.22%)	3.07
3	environmental sustainability policy	9 (12.50%)	19 (26.39%)	13 (18.06%)	19 (26.39%)	12 (16.67%)	3.08
4	environmental friendly IT purchasing policy	9 (12.86%)	14 (20.00%)	22 (31.43%)	17 (24.29%)	8 (11.43%)	3.01
5	green data centres policy	20 (30.77%)	15 (23.08%)	20 (30.77%)	9 (13.85%)	1 (1.54%)	2.32
6	policy on employees use of IT in	12 (16.90%)	15 (21.13%)	14 (19.72%)	24 (33.80%)	6 (8.45%)	2.96

	an energy efficient manner						
7	IT Hardware End of Life management policy	22 (31.43%)	16 (22.86%)	16 (22.86%)	10 (14.29%)	6 (8.57%)	2.46
8	Green Information Technology Policy	22 (30.14%)	14 (19.18%)	15 (20.55%)	20 (27.40%)	2 (2.74%)	2.53
9	corporate social responsibility policy	9 (12.16%)	20 (27.03%)	16 (21.62%)	21 (28.38%)	8 (10.81%)	2.99
	CLUSTER	132(20.09%)	137(20.85%)	146(22.22%)	150(22.83%)	75(11.42%)	2.83

Table 2: Green-Readiness Practice

S/N	Our institution has a policy that states that :	Not at all (1)	Small Extent (2)	Moderate Extent (3)	Great Extent (4)	Very Great Extent (5)	μ
1	print on both sides of the paper (duplex printing) if necessary	8 (11.11%)	9 (12.50%)	23 (31.94%)	22 (30.56%)	10 (13.89%)	3.24
2	turn off all peripherals devices (printer, scanner, projector, etc.) when not in use for a long time	4 (5.48%)	9 (12.33%)	11 (15.07%)	28 (38.36%)	21 (28.77%)	3.73
3	shortens IT equipment refresh periods to gain access to more energy efficient equipment	13 (19.12%)	17 (25.00%)	18 (26.47%)	13 (19.12%)	7 (10.29%)	2.76

4	considers environmental factors in the design of the site infrastructure (and network) of data centres servers ,storage	9 (12.86%)	19 (27.14%)	24 (34.29%)	14 (20.00%)	4 (5.71%)	2.79
5	audits the power efficiency of existing IT system and technologies	10 (14.49%)	13 (18.84%)	27 (39.13%)	13 (18.84%)	6 (8.70%)	2.88
6	switches off data centre lights and equipment when not needed	6 (8.33%)	15 (20.83%)	12 (16.67%)	25 (34.72%)	14 (19.44%)	3.36
7	enforces PC power management	11 (15.71%)	18 (25.71%)	15 (21.43%)	17 (24.29%)	9 (12.86%)	2.93
8	analyses energy bill separately from the overall corporate bill	21 (31.34%)	12 (17.91%)	11 (16.42%)	16 (23.88%)	7 (10.45%+)	2.64
	CLUSTER	82(14.24%)	112(19.44%)	141(24.5%)	148(25.7%)	78 (13.54%)	3.04

Table 3: Green-Readiness Practice- IT Sourcing

S/N		Not at all (1)	Small Extent (2)	Moderate Extent (3)	Great Extent (4)	Very Great Extent (5)	μ
1	Our institution : gives weight to environmental considerations in IT procurement	6 (8.57%)	22 (31.43%)	16 (22.86%)	19 (27.14%)	7 (10.00%)	2.99

2	gives preference of IT suppliers that have a green track record	12 (17.14%)	13 (18.57%)	23 (32.86%)	16 (22.86%)	6 (8.57%)	2.87
	CLUSTER	18(12.86%)	35(25%)	39(27.86%)	35(25%)	13(9.3%)	2.93

Table 4: G-readiness Practice-IT End of Life Practice

S/N	Our institution has:	Not at all (1)	Small Extent (2)	Moderate Extent (3)	Great Extent (4)	Very Great Extent (5)	μ
1	recycles consumables equipment (e.g. batteries, ink cartridges, and paper)	32 (43.84%)	12 (16.44%)	5 (6.85%)	15 (20.55%)	9 (12.33%)	2.41
2	discard of unwanted IT equipment in an environmental friendly way	15 (21.74%)	16 (23.19%)	12 (17.39%)	14 (20.29%)	12 (17.39%)	2.88
	CLUSTER	47(32.19%)	28(19.18%)	17(11.64 %)	29(19.86 %)	21(14.38 %)	2.65

The first objective of this study is to assess institutional policy in the area of IT sourcing, IT operations and IT end of life management to adopt Green Computing. Participants were requested to rate their institutions status and position with respect to Green-Readiness policy based on the listed items in table 1. This was to assess the existing green-readiness initiatives in the selected institutions.

The cluster mean (as stated in table1) for Green readiness policy in the selected institutions was above average ($\mu =2.83$). This showed that averagely speaking, initiatives and pronouncements on green IT readiness existed in the institutions. However, specific Green Information Technology Policy was not in place in more than 30% of the institution. Also the results indicated showed that developing green data centre and efficient disposal of e-wastes were low the overall scores under these initiatives were low with respective means of $\mu =2.32, 2.46$. However energy conserving practices such as “turning off all peripherals devices (printer, scanner, projector, etc.) when not in use for a long time” enjoy more publicity among other policy pronouncements. On IT operations, printing on both sides of the paper

(duplex printing) when necessary (with $\mu=3.24$) constituted the highest green computing operation while analysing energy bill separately from the overall corporate bill ($\mu=2.64$) was the least. Overall green computing practices were reasonably high with $\mu= 3.04$. On IT sourcing, an average of $\mu=2.94$ was obtained from scores of the items bordering on procurement of eco-friendly IT resources.

The IT end of life practice is of average score of $\mu=2.65$. Recycling consumables equipment (e.g. batteries, ink cartridges, and paper) was not prominent in institutional policy pronouncement with $\mu = 2.41$. However discarding of unwanted IT equipment in an environmental friendly way is gradually gaining popularity with item mean that was above average $\mu = 2.88$.

The second objective of the study was to assess IT governance of the selected institutions. Green ICT Governance deals with how the institutions administer green IT initiatives. Items bordering on green computing initiatives were rated by the respondents on a likert scale. The descriptive result of the responses are as stated in table 5. From table 5, 38.57% of the respondents indicated neutrality while 36.08% (14.29% Strongly disagree and 21.79% disagree) had negative response concerning the top management involvement in green IT initiatives. Only 25.09% reported positive response regarding G-readiness Governance.

TABLE 5: G-READINESS GOVERNANCE IN SELECTED UNIVERSITIES

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	μ
Top management is involved in Green IT initiative	7 (10.00%)	11 (15.71%)	27 (38.57%)	19 (27.14%)	6 (8.57%)	3.09
Our institution has defined a role for coordinating our business's green initiatives	10 (14.29%)	10 (14.29%)	28 (40.00%)	15 (21.43%)	7 (10.00%)	2.99
Top management has allocated the required resources to adopt Green IT	10 (14.71%)	19 (27.94%)	22 (32.35%)	15 (22.06%)	2 (2.94%)	2.71
Our management (or equivalent) plays a leading role in all green (IT and non-IT) initiatives	8 (11.76%)	12 (17.65%)	31 (45.59%)	14 (20.59%)	3 (4.41%)	2.88
Our institution has earmarked a budget and other resources for Green IT	7 (11.11%)	14 (22.22%)	28 (44.44%)	11 (17.46%)	3 (4.76%)	2.83

Our institution has established metrics for assessing the impact of Green IT initiatives	8 (11.76%)	16 (23.53%)	30 (44.12%)	11 (16.18%)	3 (4.41%)	2.78
Our institution has mechanisms for monitoring IT suppliers green performance	8 (11.59%)	14 (20.29%)	28 (40.58%)	16 (23.19%)	3 (4.35%)	2.88
IT department is responsible for its own electricity costs	20 (28.57%)	23 (32.86%)	18 (25.71%)	4 (5.71%)	5 (7.14%)	2.30
CLUSTER:	78 (14.29%)	119 (21.79%)	212 (38.83%)	105 (19.23%)	32 (5.86%)	2.81

The third objective of the research was to identify the factors that might prevent institutions from adopting green solution. As shown in Table 3, 45.13% of respondents (27.58% agree and 17.5% strongly) agreed that cost of green IT solutions and lack of budgetary allocation (43.28%) might prevent their institution from adopting green IT. The mean of 3.27 showed high support for the position that the factor outlined in the table might affect their institution from the adoption of green IT.

TABLE 6: FACTORS THAT MIGHT PREVENT SELECTED UNIVERSITIES FROM ADOPTING GREEN IT

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	μ
Cost of Green IT solutions	5 (7.81%)	7 (10.94%)	18 (28.13%)	22 (34.38%)	12 (18.75%)	3.45
No budget is allocated for Green IT	6 (8.96%)	12 (17.91%)	20 (29.85%)	17 (25.37%)	12 (17.91%)	3.25
Inadequate skill or training in Green IT area	6 (8.82%)	14 (20.59%)	21 (30.88%)	18 (26.47%)	9 (13.24%)	3.15
Institutional resistance to change	11 (16.42%)	20 (29.85%)	17 (25.37%)	12 (17.91%)	7 (10.45%)	2.76
No enforcement by the government	6 (8.96%)	7 (10.45%)	22 (32.84%)	17 (25.37%)	15 (22.39%)	3.42

Lack of Government incentives for Green IT implementation	7 (10.29%)	8 (11.76%)	13 (19.12%)	17 (25.00%)	23 (33.82%)	3.60
Lack of Top management support	8 (12.12%)	17 (25.76%)	18 (27.27%)	14 (21.21%)	9 (13.64%)	2.98
CLUSTER:	67 (9.88%)	111 (16.37%)	194 (28.61%)	187 (27.58%)	119 (17.55%)	3.27

DISCUSSION

The study obtained that most of the institutions under investigations had policies in place to enhance the practice of green computing. The response to most of the items were above average except for the availability of a green data center policy and IT hardware End of Life Management. .Data centers were very useful infrastructure at supporting technology information and helps at reducing the level of energy consumption and carbon emission. Data centers were very expensive to establish and maintain, in China, the data centers accounted for 2.71% and are expected to be 4.05% of the national electricity consumption in 2025 (Zhang, Chao, Tian, Meny, Zhang, Niu, Deen; 2021).Carbon emissions in China has been reduced from 98.55 million in 2018 to about 94.85 million in 2020 (Liu et al, 2021)

The United States, European Union and other nations have adopted the use of data centers for the reduction of energy use and energy saving techniques. As at 2023, there were 2701 centers in the U.S, 487 in Germany and 456 in the United Kingdom but only 2 centers in the whole of Nigeria (Taylor, 2023). If all the data centers in Nigeria were 2, it is very clear why the institutions could hardly afford any.

End of life management was also low as well as policies put in place by the institutions. This perhaps deduced from the fact that Nigeria itself as a nation does not have green computing components in the various environmental protection policies. It was felt (as earlier stated) that the various environmental protection policies and legislations did not envisage the current level of advancement in computer technology use (Nwakwo, Akinola & Ukhurebo; 2020).In the same way, written guidelines for a sustainable and proper management of the environment but no specific statements of policy are directly pointing to the management by either green procurement, green use and green disposal of computer parts. The Nigerian environmental policy was last revised in 2016 and it is long overdue for another revision to include policies on green sustainability vis-à-vis, green computing.

On green-readiness practice, it was reported that the institutions actually have some green practices and the highest among them is the turning off of all peripheral devices when not in use over time. This may be the result of individual consciousness and the national increase in electricity bills in Nigeria while the least

practices is the analysis of energy bill of computers being separated from overall corporate bills. Most institutions have all their billing systems on the same readers and have not seen the necessity of having separate readers for computer equipment. This activity if considered can further assist at introducing more green practices which will lead to a greater or more efficient use of green infrastructure.

IT sourcing and procurement involve the purchase of computers and accessories from suppliers who have particular specifications that are environmentally friendly. And the higher percentage of the respondents have low response to that. This may be so since the institutions and the IT supplier in most cases have no direct contact with the manufacturers of this IT equipment, they are forced to buy whatever they see in the market because our IT equipment are all imported from the advanced nations of Europe, U.S.A, Japan and China. Oftentimes, these equipment are dumped on African nations after use, which Ghana has identified as the worst hit by e-waste dumping (Minter, 2016)

The end of life practice is also low, this appear to be easily observable in Nigeria as electronic waste disposal are carelessly done. Urgent efforts are needed in tackling this hazardous practice.

Green readiness governance is also a little above average. The respondents are not too confident their institution top management has governance practice in place to administer green IT. A certain percentage are neutral while a higher percentage do not agree their institutions their institution adopts green IT. This supports Wabwoba et al (2012) position that green readiness level in developing economies is lower than that of developed economies. Mouakket & Aboelmaged (2021) and Martins et al. (2019) found out that organizational support greatly influenced the Green IT adoption and concluded that management commitment and support for Green IT is essential for its adoption. However, in this study the level of management support in the institutions is found out to be above average and this in turn can be related to factors that could inhibit. From the respondent data it can be observed the non-compliance in governance, conduct and practice of green IT is due to some factors like cost of green IT solutions, inadequate skill, lack of enforcement for the government and lack of incentives from government to encourage green IT.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concluded that the institutions under study have some green readiness IT policies in place, the method of e-waste disposal is still a challenge in the institutions, though some policies are in existence but facilities to actually make for green management such as a data centre were absent in all the institutions. Governance of green IT were minimal meaning that the governing bodies were

hardly involved in the management of the available facilities and monitoring of compliance with existing policies. Government incentives were also discovered to be low. In the light of these, it is therefore recommended that policies be developed and enforced on IT sourcing, use and disposal. IT professionals and users should be trained on the use of and the advantages of green IT. If the understanding of users are improved there will be less need for monitoring before compliance. There should be a budgetary allocation for green practices by the institutions and the government should also come to the aid of these institutions by providing fund for such allocations. Data centres should be built in universities and even in the country where the quantity of poisonous gasses being emitted by IT equipments can be controlled and reasonably reduced.

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